

TREATMENTS FOR SPIDER AND VARICOSE VEINS:

Spider and Varicose Veins

Spider and varicose veins are general conditions found in most adults affecting their physical appearance. These unusually enlarged veins appear mostly in the legs of the women compared to men. According to a conducted research, these abnormalities affect up to fifty percent of the adult population. Get **vein treatment**, if you experience abnormal veins.

What Are Spider Veins?

Spider veins are also known as telangiectasias. These are clusters of very small blood vessels that grow on the surface of the skin. Their appearance is generally in the red or purple color making a spider web structure. Generally, they are found on the surface of the skin or legs. Get [veins treatment near me](#) to eliminate them.

What Are Varicose Veins?

Varicose veins are unusually stretched veins that are often seen on the legs or face. They are blue, purple, or skin-colored. Moreover, they appear as enlarged, twisting, and bulging that may be raised above the surface of the skin. Get **varicose vein treatment near me** in Manhattan, if the veins are causing severe problems.

What Causes Spider and Varicose Veins?

Both kinds of veins are caused due to fundamental abnormalities of blood vessels. Scientifically, veins transport blood back to the heart from other parts of the body. To complete this task, they use a series of one-way valves to prevent the back-flow of blood.

But when these valves become defective and fail to complete their task properly, blood starts pooling within the veins. As a result, the blood pressure increases in the veins causing weak vein walls leading to varicose or spider veins. Such types of treatment require **vein treatment li**.

Vein treatment new york: Sclerotherapy

Sclerotherapy is one of the most common procedures to treat these abnormal veins. The following **varicose vein treatment in new york** can be performed in your doctor's office. A **vein specialist near me in midtown** will inject a saline solution directly to the abnormal veins resulting in collapsed veins and eventually they fade away. You may have to visit a [vein doctor near me NY](#) more than once for effective results. There may be some side effects including bruising, swelling, bleeding, infection, and skin discoloration.

Laser Therapy:

Laser therapy is another method that is also performed at your doctor's office. In some cases, it is used as a complement to sclerotherapy to get maximum results. It is always the most effective method to eliminate spider or varicose veins. People who have trauma for needles can opt for this option. Moreover, only a specialist can suggest the best suitable treatment option for you.

In this treatment, the vein doctors will use a beam of light to heat up the damaged veins making them shrink. Eventually, the body absorbs the treated veins in itself. Side effects of the treatment may include minor redness or swelling around the treated area, skin discoloration, blisters, and unusual scarring.

Intense Pulsed Light (IPL) therapy is a modern and recently designed treatment for spider veins, IPL transmits pulses of different ranges of light to the abnormal veins.